

Why more than two viewing directions for GAIA?

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1 Introduction

This note addresses the scientific desirability of basing the GAIA measurements not on a single basic angle, but on at least two different (incommensurable) basic angles. This can be realised in configurations using three or more interferometers, or two interferometers with different beam combiners. Let us consider a configuration with m (active) viewing directions, where the number m may be up to four. For $m = 1$ there is no basic angle at all, just a single field of view scanning the sky. For $m = 2$ there is one basic angle γ (if the viewing directions are connected by metrology and/or beam combiner). For $m = 3$ mutually connected viewing directions there are three basic angles γ_1 , γ_2 and $\gamma_3 = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$. For $m = 4$ the most likely configuration is that the viewing directions are operated as two independent pairs, one with basic angle γ_1 , the other with basic angle γ_2 . In this case there are no direct measurements corresponding to the angle $\gamma_1 + \gamma_2$.

We are here not concerned with the redundancy aspects of the choice of configuration, nor with the trivial photon-statistical advantage by the factor $m^{-1/2}$, assuming constant collecting area per viewing direction. Our concern is to build a maximally accurate global reference frame. This is essential for determining absolute parallaxes and distortion-free proper motions as well as for some specific applications e.g. in general relativity, and is therefore a very central scientific requirement for GAIA.

In this context the overall mission goal of $10 \mu\text{as}$ astrometric accuracy (at a certain magnitude) is not a sufficient specification of what we are aiming at. The accuracy of the reference frame depends not only on the total variance of the astrometric errors, but also on their spectral distribution in terms of different spatial frequencies or angular scale lengths. A total standard error of $10 \mu\text{as}$ may be scientifically unacceptable if most of the power is in the very low-frequency components of the error spectrum.

It is my argument that the use of more than one basic angle provides a very efficient damping of the low-frequency errors, compared with any single basic angle, and should therefore not be dismissed simply because the $10 \mu\text{as}$ goal may be achieved with a single basic angle. I will illustrate this point by means of a very simple error model.

2 Detection of low-frequency harmonics

Low-frequency error components in the astrometric reference frame must originate from low-frequency errors in the angular coordinates ('abscissae') along the scanning great circles. This is true independent of whether the data reductions are modelled on Hipparcos, using the 'great-circle reductions' as an intermediate step actually estimating the star abscissae, or if a more global-type solution is adopted (as envisaged for GAIA) in which the star abscissae do not appear explicitly. The basic problem is the same, namely that the

reference frame is built from one-dimensional measurements roughly along certain great circles, and that any systematic errors in these measurements result in systematic errors on the sphere, although damped by the multitude of scans across any given point. The abscissa is therefore a useful concept in the present discussion, even if it is not retained in the data reductions.

As function of the abscissa v , the low-frequency part of the (random or systematic) abscissa error can be written as a Fourier series with the general term $A \sin(nv + \phi)$ representing the n th harmonic. Figure 1 shows such an error component (with $n = 6$) observed through an instrument having three viewing directions each of finite width w and separated by the basic angles γ_1 , γ_2 and $\gamma_3 = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$. Within the three windows, taken together, the mean value of the abscissa error is μ , indicated by the horizontal line, and σ is the dispersion of the errors about the mean. As the windows slide around the great circle, we may compute the mean variance $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ and take this as an indication of how much this particular error harmonic would influence the observations. The possibility to detect the harmonic depends on the ratio of $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ to the variance of a typical observation. It is now easy to see why, in the case of $m = 2$, the basic angle must not be a simple fraction of the full circle: for instance, $\gamma \simeq 60$ deg makes it very difficult to detect the error component with $n = 6$, because the error is practically the same in the two fields, so that $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ becomes very small.

3 Relative variance of the low-frequency harmonics

For a certain configuration of windows, $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ is clearly proportional to the total variance of the harmonic, which is $A^2/2$. Conversely, we may say that the minimum detectable harmonic variance is inversely proportional to the $\langle \sigma^2 \rangle$ calculated for a harmonic of unit amplitude. After the data reductions, one can expect that harmonics will exist with variances which are proportional to the minimum detectable variance. We use this assumption below to calculate the relative variances of the low-frequency harmonics for different configurations of the windows.

The width w may be the geometrical width of the field of view, or perhaps rather some larger number corresponding to the interval in which the along-scan attitude can be modelled by just a few parameters. Below I have assumed $w = 2$ deg, but this value affects mainly the high-frequency harmonics and is therefore not critical for the present discussion.

For a single viewing direction ($m = 1$) I find the following expression for the relative variance of the harmonics, normalised to unity for $n = \infty$:

$$u_1(n) = \left[1 - \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{nw}{2} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

For two viewing directions connected by the basic angle γ we have:

$$u_2(n) = \left[2 - \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{nw}{2} \right) (1 + \cos n\gamma) \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where the normalisation is to m^{-1} for the high frequencies. For three viewing directions

connected by the basic angles γ_1 , γ_2 and $\gamma_3 = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$ we similarly have:

$$u_3(n) = \left[3 - \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{nw}{2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{2}{3} (\cos n\gamma_1 + \cos n\gamma_2 + \cos n\gamma_3) \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Finally for four viewing directions connected in two independent pairs with basic angles γ_1 and γ_2 we have:

$$u_4(n) = \left[4 - \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{nw}{2} \right) (2 + \cos n\gamma_1 + \cos n\gamma_2) \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

Figures 2–4 show these functions for the first 100 harmonics. $\gamma = 58$ deg was assumed for $m = 2$, as was the case for Hipparcos, while $\gamma_1 = 55$ deg, $\gamma_2 = 78.5$ deg were assumed for $m = 3$ and 4, as has been mentioned for GAIA (e.g. in Lindegren & Perryman, A&AS 116, 579, 1996).

4 Discussion and conclusion

The case of a single viewing direction ($m = 1$ in Figure 2) gives, as expected, a very poor determination of the low frequencies. Such an instrument is good for relative measurements in small areas of the sky but not for global astrometry. The use of two viewing directions with a large basic angle gives a dramatic improvement, e.g. by almost four orders of magnitude in the variance of the first harmonic (or two orders of magnitude in its amplitude). Note that the first harmonic is particularly important for the parallax determination. The Hipparcos basic angle of 58 deg was probably not completely optimal in view of the rather large relative variance of the sixth harmonic. This could have been reduced with a different basic angle, but only at the expense of increasing some other peaks. For instance, $\gamma = 56.6$ deg would reduce the maximum peak to about 14 units, but then there would be three harmonics ($n = 6, 13$ and 19) with almost the same variance $\simeq 14$ units, and their combined power would be nearly the same as for 58 deg. In fact, with a single basic angle one cannot reduce the total power of the low-frequency harmonics very significantly below the Hipparcos value.

The cases of three and four viewing directions (Figures 3 and 4) are roughly equivalent from the viewpoint of the low-frequency components. The improvement compared to $m = 2$ is an order of magnitude in the peaks, and a factor 5–6 in the mean variance of the 20 or so first harmonics.

Although it is difficult to quantify exactly the advantages of several basic angles, it is clear that the amplitude of low-frequency (‘systematic’) errors can be reduced by a very significant factor even if the total astrometric error remains the same.

Figure 1. Illustration of how a specific harmonic of the abscissa error can be detected through the dispersion (σ) of the errors observable in three windows separated by the basic angles γ_1 and γ_2 .

Figure 2. Relative variance of the error harmonics for the cases of one and two viewing directions (the latter case with basic angle $\gamma = 58$ deg).

Figure 3. Relative variance of the error harmonics for the case of three viewing directions with basic angles $\gamma_1 = 55$ deg, $\gamma_2 = 78.5$ deg and $\gamma_3 = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 133.5$ deg. The dotted curve shows for comparison the case of two viewing directions (as in Figure 2).

Figure 4. Same as Figure 3 but for four viewing directions operated as two independent pairs with basic angles $\gamma_1 = 55$ deg and $\gamma_2 = 78.5$ deg.